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Research Article

**FACTORS SUBSIDIZING TO ALTERATIONS IN THE
CONSCIOUSNESS LEVEL OF PATIENTS WITH DIABETIC
KETOACIDOSIS**¹Dr Maha Waheed, ²Dr Ali Zafar, ³Dr Alina Nazir¹House Officer, Jinnah Hospital Lahore²Medical Officer, DHQ and Teaching Hospital Sahiwal³House Officer JHL**Article Received:** February 2020**Accepted:** March 2020**Published:** April 2020**Abstract:**

Aim: The relationship between serum osmolality, glucose, sodium, bicarbonate, arterial pH, BUN and level of consciousness was studied in 189 patients with ketoacidosis (DK). Even if there was a statistically significant difference, there was a significant overlap of all laboratory values between the different groups.

Place and Duration: In the Medicine Unit II of Nishter Hospital Multan for one-year duration from March 2019 to February 2020.

Methods: To find a better predictor, we identified a new factor such as serum / arterial PH. This factor was significantly higher in sleepy and stupid patients than in drowsy and stuporous patients ($p = 0.007$ and $p = 0.03$, respectively), but it did not differ between stuporous and comatose patients ($p = 0.46$). Again, groups can overlap. There was at least one other problem, either as a coexisting or a precipitating factor, in 18 (23.3%) of the alert, 24 (29.2%) of the drowsy, 11 (43.4%) of the stuporous and 4 (57.1 %) of the comatose group.

Conclusion: It is routine to consider and exclude any of these clinical biochemical parameters as a reliable predictor of the level of consciousness in patients with DK and other altered consciousness conditions that may occur in patients with diabetes.

Key words: ketoacidosis, serum osmolality, arterial pH, level of consciousness.

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INTRODUCTION:

The level of awareness varies more or less in patients with diabetic ketoacidosis (DK). This frequency ranges between 26 and 62 percent between different observations. Only 5% have a coma¹. Reported subclinical brain function disorders are seen in patients with DK and in patients with no apparent clinical symptoms^{2,3}.

Cerebral inflammation, which is symptomatic, is fatal and is usually seen before treatment⁴.

Many factors, especially serum osmolality is thought to affect the level of awareness in these patients, but there is no definitive determinant of this neurological manifestation of DKA⁵. The need for such a predictor is emphasized, considering that many other conditions associated with altered consciousness may occur in diabetics and should be ruled out in patients with DKA⁶. In this sense, we are investigating the relationship between serum osmolality, glucose, sodium, bicarbonate, arterial pH, BU and level of awareness in DKA patients⁷.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This Prospective study was held in the Medicine Unit II of Nishter Hospital Multan for one-year duration from March 2019 to February 2020. 205 patients were selected randomly. When serum glucose > 250 mg / dL, arterial blood pH <7.30, HCO₃⁻ <15 and 1: 2 serum dilutions were considered DKA criteria, 16 patients were excluded. For each patient, the level of awareness at the admission was classified as alert, drowsy, stuporous and comatose. The Alertness was defined as alert

and fully responsive. Patients filed with a Glasgow Coma Score (GCS) were found to be 15. Somnolence is defined as a light sleep in which the patient can easily be woken by touch or noise and not fall asleep for some time. Patients filed with confused or 12-14 GCS have also been found to be drowsy. Stupor has been described as a situation in which a patient can only be awakened by strong stimuli. Patients who were said to have obtunded or 9-11 GCS were classified as stuporous. Coma has been defined as a condition in which the patient cannot be excited by stimulation. A GCS of 8 or less is thought to correspond to a coma.

During admission, serum osmolality was calculated as follows:

ANOVA $2X (Na^{++} K^{+}) (mEq / L) + glucose (mg / dL) / 18 + BU (mg / dL) / 2.8$ was used to assess the relationship between the level of consciousness and each factor. A two-sided test (-test (homoscedastic or heterodastic based on the result of the F test) was used to assess the significance of differences between the mean values of each factor for each group bilaterally. Kendall tau-b correlation coefficient was calculated as a measure of association between level of consciousness and other factors.

RESULTS:

The distribution of levels of consciousness was 77 (40.7%) in waking state, 82 (43.4%) sleepy, 23 (12.2%) stuporous and 7 (3.7%) in coma. The mean, standard deviation (SD), maximum and minimum values for each factor are summarized in Table I.

Table I. Average, standard deviations, minimum and maximum values of some laboratory findings in 189 patients with DKA

Level of Consciousnes	Osmolality (mosm/Kg) Mean±SD Min.-Max.	Glucose (mg/dL) Mean±SD Min.-Max.	Na* (mEq/L)Mean±SD Min.-Max.	pH Mean±SD Min.-Max.	HCO ₃ (mEq/L)Mean±SD D Min.-Max.
Alert	321±17 280-379	576±211 250-1430	135±5 120-148	7.17±0.08 6.93-7.30	7.87±3.6 1.9-15
Drowsy	324±20 282-379	648±281 263-1800	134±6 119-148	7.05±0.11* 6.83-7.30	4.99±3.5+ 1.4-15
Stuporous	337±26++ 300-396	715±266 400-1400	138±7 121-148	7.02±0.11 6.80-7.21	4.40±3.4 1.1-14.2
Comatose	349±36 303-407	742±283 400-1170	141±10 127-160	7.05±0.13 6.88-7.30	4.51±4.4 1.5-14.5
Total	325±21 280-407	630±256 250-1800	135±6 119-160	7.10±0.12 6.80-7.30	6.08±3.9 1.1-15

Level of consciousness was significantly associated with serum osmolality (ANOVA using <0, 01). The correlation coefficient was -0.15 (p = 0.0). This was significant when comparing drowsy with stuporous patients (p= 0.03), but not for stuporous and comatose patients (p=0.44). There was much overlap between serum osmolalities of different groups as shown in Fig. 1.

The relationship between consciousness level and arterial pH was also significant ($p < 0.001$ using ANOVA). The correlation coefficient was 0.39 ($p < 0.001$). The difference between arterial stimulus pH and drowsy patients was significant ($p < 0.001$). This was not significant when comparing drowsy with stuporous and stuporous with comatose groups ($p=0.26$ and $p=0.60$, respectively). Again, much overlap could be seen between groups (Fig. 2).

Na⁺ concentration was significantly higher in stuporous patients than in drowsy patients ($p = 0.03$), but there was no difference between alert and drowsy ($p=0.19$), and stuporous and comatose patients ($p=0.48$). The serum bicarbonate level in the drowsy group was significantly different from the stimulus group (<0.001), but not in the stuporous group ($= 0.47$). This difference was also not significant between stuporous and coma patients ($= 0.95$), in fact it was statistically the same. Other laboratory values did not differ significantly between groups. Even if the statistically significant difference was large, all laboratory values from different groups overlapped to a large extent.

The level of consciousness was significantly associated with this factor (using ANOVA $p < 0.001$). The correlation coefficient was -0.23 ($p < 0.001$). This factor was much higher in drowsy and stuporous patients than in alert and drowsy patients ($p = 0.007$) and $p = 0.03$, respectively, but did not differ between stupid and coma patients ($= 0.46$). The groups overlap, although to a lesser extent than other factors. Figure 3 shows the relationship between awareness level and serum osmolality / pH of the arteries.

In 57 (30.1%) of our patients, there was at least one other co-existing or triggering factor problem. Renal failure 2 (42.1%), urinary tract infections 13 (22.8%), pneumonia 7 (12.2%) and sepsis 4 (7%) were the most common problems. Other findings include sinusitis, pharyngitis, diabetic foot, meningitis, mediastinitis, abscess of the neck, septic arteries, shigellosis, hydatid lung cyst, heart failure after a heart attack, hemolysis due to pericardial edema, high thalassemia and G6PD deficiency. These problems showed awakening of 18 (23.3%), 2 (29.2%) sleepers and 4 (57.1%) coma groups. The exclusion of these patients did not affect the significance of differences between laboratory results of different groups.

DISCUSSION

Some authors believe that the degree of consciousness is not always correlated with the degree of clinical-biochemical symptoms of DKA, while others have found a link between the level of consciousness and many other factors. Serum osmolality, serum glucose, ketone bodies, sodium

bicarbonate, blood hydrogen ions, pH CSF and CSF concentration in ketone bodies are just some of these factors⁸. During DKA treatment, phosphate replacement was associated with better mental health, but no association was demonstrated between level of consciousness and serum phosphate.

There are studies in which a correlation between plasma glucose and awareness has been found, as well as studies showing that blood glucose does not differ significantly for unconscious and conscious DKA patients⁹. In addition, hyperglycemia is more serious if fuel oxidation is disturbed by a coma in the brain. In our study, no significant relationship was found between awareness levels and serum glucose levels. Serum osmolality has been found to be much higher in conscious patients compared to conscious patients with HBE, DKA or non-ketotic hyperglycemia¹⁰. Hyperosmolality has been shown to disrupt the functions of the central and peripheral nervous system. Fulop et al found that the modified sensorium correlates better with the size of hyperosmolality and that serious changes in the sensorium with serum osmolality <340 mosm / g should suggest a non-CAD etiology. Kitabchi et al¹¹. In the study, the calculated total osmolality was inversely proportional to the mental state, usually inversely proportional to dementia and coma observed at osmolality higher than 340 mosm / kg. They suggested that when a patient with a plasma osmolality of 340 mosm / kg or less is severely blunt or coma, a catastrophic incident other than DKA may occur. Tachibana et al. Believes that plasma osmolality between 320 and 350 mosm / kg mainly causes inhibition of the pyramidal pathway, plasma osmolality exceeding 380 mosm / g inhibits the extrapyramidal pathway, and values above 440 mosm / kg are severely suppressed¹². In this study, although stunning patients had significantly higher serum osmolality than the sleeping patient ($p = 0.03$), this did not apply to other groups and the correlation was not strong (correlation coefficient = -0.15). Serum osmolality was higher than 30 mosm / g in all our coma patients and all except one stuporous patient, but only 2 (28.5%) and 7 (30.4%) had higher serum osmolality. 340 mosm / kg. No other reason was found in two coma patients and nine stuporous patients with serum osmolality less than 340 ounces / Kg. Conversely, another cause was found in one coma patient and in three stupid patients whose serum osmolality was over 340 mosm / kg. In 16 drowsy and 9 awake patients, serum osmolality was over 340 mosm / kg.

Posner and colleagues found that mental confusion and coma occur when the pH of the cerebrospinal fluid is lowered. Assal et al¹³. have shown that the neurological deterioration of ketoacidosis is associated with normal CSF pH and bicarbonate

replacement, and progressive acidosis develops despite final neurological improvement¹⁴. Other employees could not find a correlation between blood pH and level of awareness in DKA patients. The acidosis is probably not a major cause of coma, because acidosis caused by an infusion of hydrochloric acid does not cause coma at a coma-like blood pH after administration of acetoacetic acid¹⁵. Despite being the strongest, our patients' relationships were very poor. In fact, there was a patient in a coma with a pH of 7.30.

CONCLUSION:

The level of consciousness was significantly associated with the osmolality / pH ratio and there was less overlap between the groups than other factors. However, with a weak correlation coefficient and too much overlap between groups, the osmolality / pH ratio was also not a good predictor of level of consciousness.

We came to the conclusion that none of these clinical biochemical parameters can be a reliable indicator of the level of consciousness in DKA patients and other conditions associated with altered consciousness that may occur in patients with diabetes should be considered and excluded be routine.

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